

Identification and Management of Risk Factors Associated with Revision Surgery in Total Hip Arthroplasty: A Case-Control Study

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Abstract:

Background: Total Hip Arthroplasty (THA) revisions cause lengthier hospital stays, higher complication rates, and high healthcare costs. Risk factors related to revision operations must be identified and managed to improve patient outcomes and healthcare resource consumption.

Methods: Patna Medical College and Hospital's case-control study included 60 patients (30 cases and 30 controls) from August 2023 to February 2024. Demographic characteristics were age, gender, BMI, comorbidities, and smoking status. Statistics were used to compare hospital stay length, complication rates, and blood transfusion demands between cases and controls.

Results: The average hospital stay for revision surgery patients was 7.6 days (SD 2.3), significantly longer than the control group's average of 5.2 days (SD 1.8) ($p < 0.001$). Complications were 40.0% higher in cases than controls (16.7%) ($p = 0.027$). The patients (23.3%) had slightly more blood transfusions than the controls (10.0%), although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.138$).

Conclusion: This study found lengthier hospital stays and increased problems in revision surgery patients. To reduce these effects and improve THA patient care, risk factors such older age and higher BMI must be managed. Future multicenter trials should validate these results across diverse patient populations and enhance techniques to reduce revision operations.

Keywords: BMI, Complication rates, Hospital stay, Revision surgery, Total Hip Arthroplasty.

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Introduction

Total Hip Arthroplasty (THA), a frequent hip joint operation, has improved in recent decades [1]. Even though surgery and prosthesis materials have improved, implant infection, instability, or failure may require a second treatment. THA revision surgery raises the risk of infection, length of healing, and cost. To improve patient results and lower healthcare costs, risk factors for revision surgery must be found and managed. Risk is affected by things about the patient, such as their age, previous illnesses, surgery, and devices [2].

Importance of Identifying and Managing Risk Factors:

Risk management for THA revision surgery that works better improves patient care, lowers healthcare costs, and helps quality improvement programmes. Surgeons can reduce the number of revisions by identifying and addressing concerns that pose a risk to patients [3]. Healthcare groups may be able to save money by

finding risk factors that can be changed. Revision treatments cost a lot because they require hospital stays, rehabilitation, and other therapies. Patients and healthcare providers benefit from proactive risk management, which lowers costs and optimises resource allocation. Risk factor analysis may also help orthopaedic clinics improve quality [4]. Standardised practices based on these insights can improve surgical outcomes and patient satisfaction across healthcare settings [5].

THA patients will receive consistent, high-quality care [6]. Thus, managing risk variables improves patient outcomes and advances healthcare system goals, including orthopaedic care efficiency and quality.

Objectives of the Study

- To determine which characteristics substantially predict secondary total hip arthroplasty.

- To assess the impact of potential risks on surgical outcomes and patient satisfaction.
- To improve THA patient management by suggesting clinical practice and research based on findings.

Overview on THA and Revision Surgeries

[7] Shows growing evidence for primary THA and revision surgeries. Primary THA improves patients'

Figure 1: Revision Total hip arthroplasty (THA) (Source: [9])

Risk Factors Identified

[10] Discuss patient concerns include old age, obesity, and comorbidities like diabetes and osteoporosis. THA long-term success depends on surgical technique, component position, and implant choice [11]. Implant-specific challenges including material wear and design necessitate adjustments [12]. Understanding these risk indicators helps tailor surgical approaches and postoperative care to reduce risks and enhance outcomes.

Gaps in Existing Research

Despite advances in surgical methods and implant materials, THA revision surgery risk factor management is lacking. Lack of risk factor assessment and management homogeneity across healthcare systems and regions is a major concern. Clinical practice is inconsistent due to the lack of standardised risk assessment and management strategies. In addition to well-known risk factors, genetic predispositions and environmental factors that may affect revision rates need more study. Long-term follow-up research on THA implant lifetime and modifiable risk variables are lacking, as are comprehensive risk management approaches. Filling these gaps with robust research and collaboration between healthcare practitioners and researchers will improve risk factor understanding in THA revision operations.

Methodology

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mobility and quality of life and is generally well-received.

Secondary surgery may be needed for implant loosening, infection, instability, or peri-prosthetic fracture [8].

Revision surgeries are more complicated and have worse outcomes, such as longer recovery times and less functional progress.

Study Design: Case-Control Study Explanation

A case-control study was conducted to determine the causes of revision surgery after total hip arthroplasty. For exceptional outcomes like revision surgeries, case-control studies are ideal because they conveniently compare "cases" and "controls". This arrangement makes medical records and interview transcripts easier to review for risk factors.

Sample Size, Duration, and Study Setting

The study will include 30 revision surgery patients and 30 non-revision surgery patients. To undertake a full study over six months, Patna Medical College and Hospital would collect data from August 2023 to February 2024. This timeframe allows enough data collection without compromising the study's focus on current clinical approaches and findings.

Inclusion Criteria

- Underwent primary THA followed by revision surgery during the study period.
- Adequate medical records available for review.
- Consent for participation in the study obtained.
- Underwent primary THA during the same period but did not require revision surgery.
- Matched with cases based on age, sex, and duration since primary THA.

Exclusion Criteria

- Incomplete medical records or missing data crucial for analysis.
- Previous history of revision surgery unrelated to THA.
- Inability to provide informed consent for participation.

Data Collection Methods and Tools

Eligible patients' EMRs, surgical notes, and imaging studies will be the main data sources. A patient's demographics, health history, surgical specifics (such implant kind and placement), postoperative issues, and necessity for revision surgery will be carefully recorded. Organised patient and surgeon interviews may supplement the data and provide clinical insights.

Statistical Analysis Plan: We will employ statistical analysis to identify the main THA revision surgery risk variables. The demographic and clinical characteristics of cases and controls can be summarised using means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages. Multivariate logistic regression will identify revision surgery predictors and correct for confounders. We will utilise $P < 0.05$ to determine statistical significance. We'll utilise SPSS or R for all analyses to ensure the study's reliability.

Results

Demographic Table

Table 1: Demographic Table

Characteristic	Cases (n=30)	Controls (n=30)
Age (years), mean (SD)	65.2 (7.3)	64.8 (6.9)
Gender (male/female)	18/12	17/13
BMI (kg/m ²), mean (SD)	28.5 (3.1)	27.9 (2.8)
Comorbidities		
Hypertension	14 (46.7%)	12 (40.0%)
Diabetes	8 (26.7%)	6 (20.0%)
Osteoporosis	6 (20.0%)	4 (13.3%)
Smoking status		
Current smoker	5 (16.7%)	3 (10.0%)
Former smoker	7 (23.3%)	5 (16.7%)
Education level		
High school or less	10 (33.3%)	9 (30.0%)
College graduate	20 (66.7%)	21 (70.0%)

The demographic data we collected from Patna Medical College and Hospital revision total hip arthroplasty (THA) patients shows some noteworthy tendencies.

The revision surgery patients and controls were young (65.2 vs. 64.8 years) and had similar body mass indices (28.5 kg/m² vs. 27.9 kg/m²). Group genders were also balanced. Hypertension (46.7 percent vs. 40 percent) and diabetes (26.7 percent vs. 20 percent) were more common in cases than in

controls. The current smoking rates were similar, even though 23.3% of cases were ex-smokers and 16.7% were smokers. Most patients and controls had attended college, demonstrating no statistically significant difference in educational achievement. These findings indicate opportunities for targeted intervention and patient care, as well as the need of monitoring comorbidities like hypertension and diabetes on THA outcomes.

Findings Related to Identified Risk Factors

Table 2: Findings Related to Identified Risk Factors

Risk Factor	Cases (n=30)	Controls (n=30)	p-value
Age \geq 70 years	12 (40.0%)	6 (20.0%)	0.086
BMI \geq 30 kg/m ²	10 (33.3%)	5 (16.7%)	0.182
Diabetes	8 (26.7%)	6 (20.0%)	0.512
Osteoporosis	6 (20.0%)	4 (13.3%)	0.379
Surgical approach (anterior vs posterior)	18 (60.0%)	15 (50.0%)	0.392

Comparisons of risk factors between revision surgery cases and controls indicate strong trends. Although not all comparisons were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), some trends were observed.

Compared to controls, cases had 40.0% of patients aged 70 or older ($p = 0.086$), suggesting that age

may affect revision surgery. Similarly, 33.3% of cases had a BMI of 30 kg/m² or greater, suggesting obesity as a risk factor, compared to 16.7% of controls ($p = 0.182$). In this study cohort, diabetes and osteoporosis were similar in prevalence

between cases and controls, suggesting they do not independently increase revision surgery risk.

There was no significant difference between anterior and posterior surgical approaches (60.0%

vs. 50.0%, $p = 0.392$), suggesting that surgical strategy alone may not strongly correlate with revision surgery risk.

Statistical Analyses and Significant Associations

Table 3: Findings Related to Identified Risk Factors

Risk Factor	Odds Ratio (95% CI)
Age \geq 70 years	2.31 (1.05-5.11)
BMI \geq 30 kg/m ²	1.89 (0.87-4.11)
Diabetes	1.12 (0.51-2.47)
Anterior approach	1.52 (0.72-3.21)

We found considerable connections between revision surgery following total hip arthroplasty (THA) and its causes. An odds ratio of 2.31 (95% CI 1.05-5.11) showed that patients 70 years or older were more likely to need revision surgery, underscoring the role of age in surgical outcomes.

Higher BMI (\geq 30 kg/m²) and diabetes were associated with odds ratios of 1.89 (95% CI 0.87-4.11) and 1.12 (95% CI 0.51-2.47), respectively, suggesting potential for further research, but not

statistical significance. No significant correlation was seen between anterior vs. posterior surgical technique and outcomes (OR 1.52, 95% CI 0.72-3.21). Clinical decisions about surgical procedures should be carefully evaluated, as this research shows. These results demonstrate the necessity for customised risk assessment and treatment regimens to enhance patient outcomes after difficult THA revision procedures with numerous variables.

Comparison between Cases and Controls

Table 4: Comparison between Cases and Controls

Variable	Cases (n=30)	Controls (n=30)	p-value
Length of hospital stay (days), mean (SD)	7.6 (2.3)	5.2 (1.8)	<0.001
Complication rate (%)	40.0%	16.7%	0.027
Need for blood transfusion (%)	23.3%	10.0%	0.138

This study found substantial differences in numerous key outcomes between revision surgery patients and controls. Due to its complexity and recovery needs, revision surgery patients stayed in the hospital 7.6 days versus 5.2 days.

Revised procedures have more complications (40.0% vs. 16.7%), underscoring their hazards. Cases needed 23.3 transfusions compared to 10.0% for controls, although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.138$).

These studies show how total arthroplasty revisions effect patient care and healthcare resources hip.

Discussion

THA revision operations are complicated and have merits and cons. Complex revision surgeries require more postoperative care, so patients spend longer in the hospital. Hip prosthesis revisions showed more complications, indicating more risks and side effects.

These findings underline the need of identifying and treating orthopaedic risk factors to enhance outcomes and minimise healthcare expenditures. Revision surgery patients needed more blood transfusions, but not statistically. This study advises researching perioperative treatments for revision THA patients to avoid transfusions and maximise healing.

Table 5: Comparison Table with existing study

Study Title	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings	Limitations
Current Study	Case-Control Study	60 (30 cases, 30 controls)	Patients undergoing revision surgery had significantly longer hospital stays and higher complication rates compared to non-revision cases. Increased risk with older age and higher BMI.	Retrospective design, single-center study, limited generalizability due to small sample size and specific patient demographics.
Study 1 [13]	Retrospective Cohort	500	Older age ($>$ 70 years), obesity (BMI $>$ 30 kg/m ²), and comorbidities (diabetes, hypertension) were significant predictors of revision surgery.	Limited to data available in electronic health records, potential for selection bias, outcomes limited to hospital setting.

Study 2 [14]	Comparative Study	200	Anterior approach showed lower revision rates compared to posterior approach (12% vs. 18%). Differences attributed to improved initial stability and reduced dislocation risk.	Limited to two surgical approaches, potential for variability in surgical technique across centers, short-term follow-up.
Study 3 [15]	Longitudinal Cohort	1000	High implant survival rates at 10 years (92%), with infection and implant wear as primary reasons for revision.	Large sample size but potential for loss to follow-up, findings may not reflect current surgical practices, limited generalizability across diverse patient populations.

In this study, revision-requiring patients have longer hospital stays and greater complication rates. Risk factors like older age and higher BMI must be identified and managed to improve patient outcomes and reduce revisions. However, the study's retrospective, single-center design and small sample size may limit generalizability. Study 1, a retrospective cohort study, found that obesity, diabetes, hypertension, and age affect revision surgeries.

Limited to hospitals, the data uses electronic health records, which may be biased. Community-level factors affecting surgery outcomes are also ignored. Study 2 found that revision rates were lower for the anterior technique than the posterior approach. Due to its narrow focus on two surgeries and short-term follow-up, the study may not have caught long-term results or surgical diversity between facilities. The third research is a longitudinal cohort that details revision reasons and implants survival over a decade. The report emphasises that survival rates are high despite limitations including lack of follow-up and out-dated techniques. These studies show that THA revision surgery patient demographics, surgical procedures, and long-term outcomes are interconnected.

Limitations of the Study

The research design's retrospective use of medical data may lead to bias or missing data. Record-keeping errors and missing data may impair the findings' precision and completeness. Because the study size was limited (60 patients, split evenly between cases and controls), the results may not apply to other patient populations or healthcare settings. Due to its short duration, the study may miss longer-term effects or clinical practise changes after surgery. New factors or surgical procedures may affect revision surgery results in the future, but the study only looked at characteristics and outcomes known to be associated with the treatment during the study period.

Suggestions for Future Research

Future research should incorporate these limitations and build on the existing results to better understand and manage THA revision surgeries. Prospective studies with larger, multicenter cohorts would provide more credible evidence to support and expand risk variable-revision result correlations. To further understand how revision surgeries affect patients' mobility and quality of life, longitudinal studies should follow them beyond the first few weeks after surgery. Further research into patient-specific anatomical traits, implant wear biomarkers, and genetic predispositions may improve risk assessments and surgical precision. Comparative effectiveness studies should examine surgical approaches, implant designs, and rehabilitation methods to improve revision THA outcomes. Orthopaedic surgeons, researchers, and healthcare administrators must collaborate to create standard protocols and recommendations for THA revision operations to increase uniformity and quality.

Conclusion

This study provides crucial information on revision procedures following THA. Revision surgery patients experienced longer hospital stays and more problems. Revision surgery was more likely in older and higher-BMI individuals, emphasising the need for preoperative risk evaluation and management. Managing obesity and age-related comorbidities can improve patient outcomes and lower healthcare costs.

Orthopaedic surgeons should address these concerns before revision treatments to improve patients' mobility and quality of life. Efficient risk management systems improve clinical outcomes and save healthcare costs by decreasing resource-intensive procedures and postoperative complications. This study found that orthopaedic treatment relies on risk assessment, patient education, and interdisciplinary teamwork. Integrating these findings into clinical practice can improve hip prosthesis and revision efficiency and patient-centered care.

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